

Short Article on the topic: Role of Judiciary in protecting human rights in India

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Abstract: This Article provides an introduction of how judiciary has played an important role in protecting human rights in India. Human rights are basic rights which every person on this earth is entitled to have. India is a democratic Country and every citizen is entitled to exercise their rights given under the Constitution. Every citizen has given some basic rights which when violated then, they can directly approach the Judicial Courts regarding it. Judicial Courts have given number of Judgements in which fundamental rights of the citizens were given preference.

Role of Judiciary in protecting human rights in India

Each individual is entitled to some rights which are inherent to human existence. Such rights should not be violated on the grounds of gender, race, caste, ethnicity, religion, etc., these are called human rights. Section 2(1)(d) of the Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993 defines the words "Human Rights" as under: "Human Rights" means the rights relating to life, equality and dignity of the individual guaranteed by the Constitution or embodied in the International Covenants and enforceable by courts in India." Human rights are also called as basic rights, fundamental rights, natural or inherent rights. Human Rights are rights that belong to every person and they are not dependent on specifics of the individual. Human Rights are moral, pre-legal rights and cannot be granted by people or taken away by them. Human Rights have been recognized by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and adopted as Fundamental Rights in Part III of our Constitution.¹

India is the biggest democracy and the main objective of the Constitution is to protect the rights of the people. Part III of the Constitution deals with Fundamental rights whereas, Part IV deals with Directive Principles of State Policy. The Fundamental Rights are the basic rights of all citizens. Article 32 of the Constitution of India is known as heart and soul of the Constitution. It deals with 'Right to Constitutional remedies'. If any right given under part III of COI is violated then he/she can approach the Supreme Court directly. It is a fundamental right of every citizen. A person can also file a writ petition if his/her Fundamental Rights have been infringed by the State. This is given under Article 226 of the COI.

Judiciary is the ultimate guardian of the Human rights. It has interpreted fundamental rights and protects not only the enumerated rights in the Constitution but also the unenumerated rights. In *Maneka Gandhi v. UOI*,² the Supreme Court interpreted the Right to life and widen its scope and deduced an unenumerated right as Right to live with human dignity. Thereafter, in many cases like *People's Union for Civil Liberties & another v. State of Maharashtra & others*,³ and *Francis Coralie Mullin v. The Administrator, Union Territory of Delhi*,⁴ held

¹ National Legal Services Authority Vs. Union of India, (2014) 5 SCC 438.

² AIR 1978 SC 597.

³ (2014) 10 SCC 635.

⁴ (1980) 2 SCR 557.

that Right to life include Right to live with human dignity. Right to life is one of the basic human rights and not even the State has the authority to violate that right.⁵

Public Interest Litigation (PIL) permits public spirited persons to file a writ petition for enforcement of rights of any other person or a class, if they are unable to invoke the jurisdiction of Court due to poverty or any other social and economic problem. In *S.P Gupta v. UOI & Ors*,⁶ Supreme Court held that any member of the public can approach the Court for enforcing the Constitutional or legal rights of those who cannot go to Court because of poverty or any other disability. And similar observation was made in cases like *Bandhua Mukti Morcha v. UOI*,⁷ and *Narmada Bachao Andolan v. UOI*.⁸ Therefore PIL has become the tool for the protection of human rights of the people in India.

The oppressed sections of society are more prone to violation of Human rights. Most vulnerable sections of society are children, women and socially & educationally weaker section of society. Judiciary has taken up steps to protect these sections of the society. United Nations Convention on Rights of Child (UNCRC) was adopted in 1989 for the protection of rights of children. This Convention brings together children's human rights. Judiciary has also played a vital role in protecting the rights of children in India. There are various instances where Judiciary intervened to protect the rights of children. In Labourers working on *Salal project v. State of Jammu & Kashmir*,⁹ the Supreme Court held that children below age of 14 years are not allowed to work in construction project. The Court also issued various directions related to child labour. In *Vishal Jeet v. UOI*,¹⁰ the Court asked government to setup an advisory committee to make suggestions for eradication of child prostitution and to evolve schemes which should take proper care of victim girls and children. In *Gaurav Jain v. UOI*,¹¹ the Court focused on rehabilitation of minors involved in prostitution and said that juveniles must be used as rehabilitation centres for such children. The Mumbai High Court in *Public at large v. State of Maharashtra*,¹² rescued children from flesh and trade and passed order for checking sexual slavery of children and for their rehabilitation. In another case of *PUCL v. UOI*,¹³ the children were kept as bonded labour, the Supreme Court released them and also ordered for grant of

⁵ Siddharam Satlingappa Mhetre v. State of Maharashtra, JT 2010 (13) SC 247.

⁶ AIR 1982 SC 149.

⁷ (1997) 10 SCC 549.

⁸ AIR 2008 MP 142.

⁹ (1984) 3 SCC 538.

¹⁰ 1990 AIR 1412.

¹¹ 1990 AIR 292.

¹² 1997 (4) Bom CR 171.

¹³ AIR 1997 SC 568.

compensation to them. In *Bandhua Mukti Morcha case* the SC ordered compulsory education vis-à-vis eradication of child labour.

Despite Article 14 of COI women are subjected to discrimination. Article 39 of COI guarantees of equal pay for equal work for both men and women, but then also women are not treated equally. Supreme Court has played a very important role in protection of their rights. In *Associate Bank Officers association v. State Bank of India*,¹⁴ the Supreme Court held that women workers are in no way inferior to their male counterparts and hence there should be no discrimination on the ground of sex against women. In another case of *State of Madhya Pradesh v. Pramod Bhatiya*,¹⁵ SC held that under Article 39 the State shall direct its policy towards securing equal pay for equal work for both men and women. Under ambit of Art 21, protection of life and personal liberty was invoked for the dignified life for the prostitutes by SC in case of *State of Maharashtra v. Madhukar Narayan Handlikar*,¹⁶ the Court held that even the women of easy virtue are entitled to privacy and no one can evade her privacy. In the landmark judgement of *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan*,¹⁷ SC laid down the guidelines for protection of women against sexual harassment at work place. Similarly, in *Medha Kotwal Lele v. UOI*,¹⁸ guidelines for ensuring the safe work environment for women were given.

The Supreme Court in *People's Union for Democratic Rights v. UOI*,¹⁹ stated that releasing persons from bonded labours was connected to rehabilitation of persons in order to give full remedy. The Court has also protected the rights of the Prisoners in *Prem Shankar v. Delhi Administration*,²⁰ the court held that practice of using handcuff and fetters on prisoners violates the guarantee of human dignity. In another landmark judgement of *D.K Basu v. State of West Bengal*,²¹ the rights of prisoners were protected and court laid down various guidelines for arrest and detention to prevent the custodial violence and observed that right to life include right to live with human dignity. Similarly, in case of *Sheela Barse v. UOI*,²² which deals with the issue of mistreatment of women in police station. The court laid down various guidelines for protection of rights of women in custodial institution. Further, in *Citizens for Democracy*

¹⁴ 1996 11 SCC 348.

¹⁵ AIR 1993 SC 286.

¹⁶ AIR 1991 SC 207.

¹⁷ (1997) 6 SCC 241.

¹⁸ (2013) 1 SCC 311.

¹⁷ 1983 SCR (1) 456.

²⁰ AIR 1980 SC 1535.

²¹ (1997) 1 SCC 416.

²² 1986 SCC (3) 596.

v. State of Assam & Ors,²³ the SC held that the handcuffing and tying with ropes is inhumane and violates human rights guaranteed under the international laws and laws of the land. Handcuffing can be done only by taking the permission of magistrate.

As the many legislations and judicial rulings of the Hon'ble Supreme Court listed above show, the judiciary must play a significant role in the preservation of citizens' human rights. It is the subordinate judiciary that can intervene first and quickly to save a citizen whose human rights are being violated by the police, jail, or other executive institutions. The subordinate judiciary will play a critical role in defending citizens' human rights in the future.

The subordinate judiciary will play a critical role in defending citizens' human rights in the future. Aside from the State Human Rights Commissions and the National Human Rights Commission, the special courts established under the 1993 Protection of Human Rights Act need to be granted broader authority to deal with complaints of human rights violations. It is hoped that the situation regarding the respect and preservation of human rights in the country will improve in the coming days.

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²³ (1995) 3 SCC 743.